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› PENDLERRATD

Findings from a research project promoting a gamification platform for commuters as enabler for long-term active mobility

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■ About PenderRatD

- The PenderRatD (Bonus) App
- Outlook

P E N D
L E R
R A T D

THE MAIN GOAL OF PENDLERRATD: MOTIVATE TO USE THE BICYCLE INSTEAD OF CAR FOR COMMUTING

Change means of transport from car to bicycle

PendlerRatD app

PendlerRatD across Germany

■ Goal:

- Encourage motorized commuters to switch from vehicles with internal combustion engines to sustainable mobility options.
- Provide long-term support via an app for mobile devices.
- As part of the project, a mobile platform (native app) is to be developed & piloted along with a communication and community building campaign.
- Results from PendlerRatD are to be rolled out across Germany in a three-stage process.

CONVINCED CAR COMMUTERS WERE IDENTIFIED AND MOTIVATED TO USE THE BICYCLE

The project consists of a four-stage model

Stage 1: Questionnaire (2019)

- First, in the beginning of 2019, an extensive questionnaire was administered to gain insights into the current situation of commuters in the Stuttgart metropole area.
- Sample size: larger than 2.500

Stage 2: Pilotphase 1 (2019)

- Second, 200 participants of aforementioned study got the chance to test-ride pedelecs for four weeks to work to provide their commuting data based on gps-tracks and personal insights.

Stage 3: Pilotphase 2 (2020)

- Third, a second questionnaire was rolled out and a pilot phase started in 2020, lasting for seven months
- More than 125 participants commuted to work by bicycle and took part in data tracking and survey activities

Stage 4: Data analysis

- The whole data was analyzed and evaluated.
- The project is going to be rolled out throughout Germany from 2022 to 2024.

CONCLUSION OF THE PENDLERRATD-PILOTPHASES: KEY RESULTS

PENDLERRAT PLATFORM ACCOMPANIES EMPLOYEES THROUGHOUT THE ENTIRE COMMUTING PROCESS

PENDLERRATD BONUS MODULE: INCENTIVES CAN BE SET FOR COMMUNTING BY BIKE

- With the bonus module, employers have the opportunity to **reward their employees for commuting by bike or intermodal solutions** and thus drive the mobility revolution.
- The employer provides various bonuses** (e.g., canteen meals or cycling equipment, etc.) and specifies how many journeys and/or how many kilometers and/or how many meters of altitude must be performed in order to redeem a certain bonus.
- Employees can track their commutes** via the PendlerratD app. Furthermore, it will be possible to **upload gpx files** in the future. For this purpose, the employees create a PendlerratD profile.

MONITORING MODULE: TRANSPARENCY ABOUT ADVANTAGES/DISADVANTAGES OF A VEHICLE

- The **monitoring module calculates the switching effects** of changing a mode of transportation on the commuter themselves (their health), on the environment and on costs.
- In the monitoring module, three indices are created based on the distances commuted by bike: **a fit index, a green index, and a cost index.**
- The respective indices are calculated on the basis of **personal data** such as age and weight as well as **commuting data** on the mode of transport predominantly used at present compared with the use of a bicycle or pedelec.
- These inputs allow the calculation of switching effects and indices on an aggregate form of **bicycle use compared to the previously used/other mode of transportation**

Meine PendlerratD-Bilanz

Hier sehen Sie die Umstiegeffekte, die auf denen von Ihnen angegebenen Daten basieren.
 Mit einem Klick auf "Mehr erfahren" können Sie weitere Kennzahlen zu dem jeweiligen Bereich und die daraus resultierende Bilanz einsehen.

THANK YOU!

Please refer any questions to:

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